

EVALUATION OF CARTILAGE DAMAGE IN OSTEOARTHRITIS OF THE KNEE: A COMPARATIVE STUDY OF CONVENTIONAL RADIOGRAPHY, ULTRASONOGRAPHY, AND MRI

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ABSTRACT

Background and Aims: Osteoarthritis (OA) is a prevalent degenerative joint disease impacting the musculoskeletal system, especially the knee joint, causing pain, disability, and economic burden. Traditional diagnosis primarily relies on conventional radiography, which is limited in detecting early cartilage and soft-tissue changes. Emerging imaging techniques, such as ultrasonography (USG) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), offer non-invasive and detailed evaluations of cartilage and soft tissue. This study aimed to compare the efficacy of conventional radiography, USG, and MRI in assessing cartilage damage in knee OA to inform optimal diagnostic approaches.

Methods: *This prospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Radiodiagnosis, N.S.C.B. Subharti Medical College, Meerut, from August 2022 to June 2024, including 102 patients aged 20-70 years with clinically suspected knee OA. Ethical approval and informed consent were obtained. Imaging assessments with X-ray, USG, and MRI were performed following standardized protocols. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.*

Results: *Among 102 cases, females constituted 61.8% and males 38.2%, indicating a higher prevalence in females. X-ray and MRI were particularly effective for identifying advanced OA cases, while USG showed sensitivity in early detection. Combining these modalities enhanced diagnostic accuracy by capturing both bony and soft-tissue changes.*

Conclusion: *Integrating conventional radiography, USG, and MRI provides a comprehensive assessment of knee OA, supporting better diagnostic accuracy and treatment planning, particularly in advanced cases.*

Subject: *Orthopedic Imaging and Diagnostics in Knee Osteoarthritis*

Keywords: Osteoarthritis, Knee, Radiography, Ultrasonography, Magnetic Resonance Imaging

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INTRODUCTION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is the most common degenerative disorder affecting the musculoskeletal system, particularly among the elderly, with a pronounced impact on knee joints. (1,2) Knee OA has a prevalence rate of 28.7% in the Indian population, (3) making it a prominent public health concern with significant implications for healthcare costs and quality of life. Known for its progressive cartilage degeneration, osteophyte formation, meniscal atrophy, and synovial inflammation, OA is not merely a “wear and tear” condition; it affects various structures within the joint and even beyond, impacting body-wide health. (1,2) Knee OA leads to chronic pain, reduced joint mobility, and substantial functional limitations, resulting in economic consequences due to work-related disability and increased healthcare demands.

Traditional diagnosis of knee OA relies on conventional radiography, widely considered the gold standard due to its accessibility and cost-effectiveness. (4,5) Conventional radiography focuses on joint space width, which reflects the cartilage and meniscal integrity indirectly through joint space narrowing and osteophyte visualization. (6,7) However, this approach has notable limitations; radiographs lack the sensitivity to detect early cartilage changes or soft tissue abnormalities, which are key indicators of OA progression. In fact, radiographic findings often correlate poorly with pain severity because they offer only an indirect view of cartilage health and cannot capture surrounding soft tissue structures that may contribute to the patient’s symptoms. (8,9,10)

Evaluation of Cartilage Damage in Osteoarthritis of The Knee: A Comparative Study of Conventional Radiography, Ultrasonography, and MRI

Recent advances in imaging have led to the adoption of ultrasonography (US) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) as alternative or complementary diagnostic tools. High-frequency musculoskeletal ultrasonography (US) allows dynamic, non-invasive, radiation-free assessment of knee OA. (11,12,23) It enables real-time visualization of superficial cartilage, effusion, and periarticular structures, making it particularly valuable for identifying early inflammatory changes. US is widely accessible, relatively affordable, and highly suitable for repeated evaluations. On the other hand, MRI remains the most precise imaging modality for OA, capable of capturing detailed structural changes in cartilage, bone marrow, meniscus, and ligaments. MRI offers a comprehensive, three-dimensional view of the knee joint, allowing clinicians to visualize cartilage composition and morphology in unparalleled detail. However, MRI's high cost and limited availability often restrict its use in routine practice. (2)

This study aimed to provide a comprehensive evaluation of cartilage damage in knee OA by comparing conventional radiography, high-frequency ultrasonography, and MRI. By exploring the strengths and limitations of each modality, this research seeks to determine the most effective approach for assessing cartilage integrity and guiding treatment planning. The findings are intended to inform best practices in imaging for knee OA, optimizing patient management and improving long-term outcomes.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Study Setting:

This study was conducted in the Department of Radiodiagnosis, Imaging, and Interventional Radiology, N.S.C.B. Subharti Medical College, C.S.S. Hospital, Meerut.

Study Design:

A prospective observational study.

Sample Size and Duration:

The study included 120 patients, carried out over a 2-year period from August 2022 to June 2024.

Study Instruments:

- Clinical proforma
- X-ray machine
- Samsung HS70A ultrasound machine
- uMR 3.0 T MRI scanner

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 20–70 years presenting with knee pain and clinically suspected osteoarthritis.

Exclusion Criteria:

1. Recent invasive procedures, surgeries, joint arthropathy, infections, or tumors within the past 6 months.
2. Patients unwilling to participate.
3. Contraindications to MRI (e.g., pacemakers, metallic implants, claustrophobia).

Methodology:

The study recruited patients referred from the orthopedics department to the radiology unit. Each patient provided informed consent after being briefed about the study protocol. A detailed history and clinical examination were performed. Imaging techniques included MRI, conventional radiography, and ultrasonography.

MRI Protocol:

MRI was performed using the uMR 780 3.0 T scanner. Patients were positioned supine with the knee immobilized in a small parts coil. Routine sequences included:

- Axial FSE & T1-weighted images
- Sagittal PD, FSE, T1, & T2-weighted images
- Coronal STIR, GRE, & T2-weighted images

The slice thickness ranged from 2–4 mm.

Ultrasonography Protocol:

USG was performed using the Samsung HS70A high-frequency linear probe. Patients were examined supine with knees extended for anterior compartments and flexed for medial and lateral femoral cartilage evaluation. Cartilage was graded into five levels based on echogenicity and thickness changes.

Radiographic Protocol:

Weight-bearing anteroposterior and lateral knee radiographs were obtained and graded using the Kellgren-Lawrence scoring system (0–4) for osteoarthritis severity.

Statistical Analysis:

Data were recorded in Excel and analyzed using SPSS software. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Ethical Considerations:

The study received ethical clearance, and informed written consent was obtained from all participants. Patient confidentiality was strictly maintained, and only standard diagnostic investigations were performed.

RESULTS

The gender distribution of the study subjects is shown in Table 1. Out of a total of 102 cases, 61.8% were female, and 38.2% were male, indicating a higher representation of females in the study.

Gender	Frequency	Percent
Female	63	61.8%
Male	39	38.2%
Total	102	100.0%

Gender Distribution of Study Subjects

The distribution of study subjects across osteoarthritis grading levels using X-ray, USG, and MRI modalities is shown in Table 2. It helps in understanding the comparative assessment of OA severity across these imaging methods.

Grade	X-ray Frequency	X-ray Percent	USG Frequency	USG Percent	MRI Frequency	MRI Percent
Grade 0	10	9.8%	11	10.8%	2	2.0%
Grade 1	25	24.5%	35	34.3%	24	23.5%
Grade 2 / 2A	19	18.6%	23	22.5%	37	36.3%
Grade 2B	-	-	15	14.7%	-	-
Grade 3	21	20.6%	18	17.6%	19	18.6%
Grade 4	27	26.5%	-	-	20	19.6%
Total	102	100.0%	102	100.0%	102	100.0%

Sensitivity, specificity, positive predictive value (PPV), negative predictive value (NPV), and accuracy of X-ray with USG, X-ray with MRI, and USG with MRI are shown in Table 3. The data provides insight into the diagnostic efficacy of each modality pairing in evaluating osteoarthritis.

Statistic	X-ray with USG Value	X-ray with USG 95% CI	X-ray with MRI Value	X-ray with MRI 95% CI	USG with MRI Value	USG with MRI 95% CI
Sensitivity	91.21%	83.41% to 96.13%	92.00%	84.84% to 96.48%	89.00%	81.17% to 94.38%
Specificity	68.18%	53.6% to 85.1%	84.2%	65.1% to 95.6%	70.00%	68.79% to 89.9%
Positive Predictive Value	90.22%	87.39% to 92.47%	100.00%	96.07% to 100.00%	97.80%	97.65% to 97.95%
Negative Predictive Value	63.2%	55.1% to 81.2%	63.8%	41.40% to 85.4%	56.3%	48.1% to 62.8%
Accuracy	83.33%	74.66% to 89.98%	92.16%	85.13% to 96.55%	87.25%	79.19% to 93.04%

DISCUSSION

Osteoarthritis (OA) is a degenerative joint disease that affects the musculoskeletal system, particularly the knee joint. It is characterized by bone erosion, osteophyte formation, cartilage degeneration, meniscus atrophy, joint effusion, and synovial inflammation. Knee OA has significant implications for healthcare due to its association with functional disability and economic burden. Conventional radiography, commonly used for OA diagnosis, assesses joint space narrowing (JSN), osteophytes, and other bony changes, although it lacks sensitivity for early cartilage changes.

Evaluation of Cartilage Damage in Osteoarthritis of The Knee: A Comparative Study of Conventional Radiography, Ultrasonography, and MRI

Recently, high-frequency musculoskeletal ultrasonography (US) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have emerged as valuable tools for assessing soft tissue and cartilage integrity in OA. In our study, out of 102 cases, 61.8% were female, indicating a female predominance similar to previous studies. **Singh et al. (5)** reported a 22:63 male-to-female ratio among OA patients, and **Chan et al. (13)** observed a 2.86 female-to-male ratio. **Podlipská et al. (2)** and **Beyers et al. (14)** found ratios of 49:30 and 2:1, respectively, while **Brom et al. (15)** reported a female-to-male ratio of 3:1. This trend highlights the greater prevalence of OA in females, likely due to hormonal and physiological differences.

X-ray remains the most accessible imaging method for OA diagnosis. The Kellgren-Lawrence (KL) grading system, based on osteophytes and JSN, is frequently employed for OA severity classification. In this study, KL Grade 1 was present in 24.5% of cases, Grade 2 in 18.6%, Grade 3 in 20.6%, and Grade 4 in 26.5%. **Naredo et al. (1)** observed radiographic evidence of femorotibial (FT) degeneration in symptomatic and asymptomatic knees, with KL Grade I in 28%, Grade II in 39%, Grade III in 30%, and Grade IV in 3% of knees. **Singh et al. (5)** found that 40% of cases were KL Grade IV, while **Brom et al. (15)** reported degenerative alterations primarily in KL Grade III. The predominance of advanced KL grades in our study may reflect the rural, agriculturally active population, who often seek medical help later in the disease course.

Joint space narrowing (JSN) and osteophytes were key radiographic markers in our study, with definite JSN in 39.2% of cases. Marginal osteophytes were prevalent, with 44.1% of cases classified as "possible osteophytes." Minimal sclerosis was observed in 34.3% of cases. **Hayashi et al. (16)** emphasized that worsening JSN is a criterion for OA progression, often culminating in joint replacement when joint space width (JSW) is completely lost.

Ultrasonography (US) offers real-time, dynamic imaging without radiation exposure. **Keen et al. (17)** and **de Miguel Mendieta et al. (18)** noted US's effectiveness in visualizing soft tissue changes in OA, such as bursitis, synovitis, and meniscal lesions. In our study, medial condylar measurements averaged 2.13 mm, while lateral condylar dimensions averaged 2.34 mm. US grading of OA revealed Grade 1 in 34.3%, Grade 2A in 22.5%, Grade 2B in 14.7%, and Grade 3 in 17.6% of cases. **Podlipská et al. (2)** found that the US effectively detected medial meniscal extrusion and osteophytes in the femorotibial area, aligning with radiographic findings. **Koski et al. (19)** reported a strong correlation between US-detected osteophytes and arthroscopic cartilage degeneration. **Serban et al. (20)** further confirmed a correlation between US-detected osteophytes, cartilage degradation, and KL grades.

MRI is considered the gold standard for cartilage assessment in OA due to its high sensitivity and specificity, although it is limited by cost and availability. In this study, MRI evaluations according to the Modified Outerbridge classification revealed medial femoral cartilage defects with Grade 1 in 20.6%, Grade 2 in 31.4%, Grade 3 in 19.6%, and Grade 4 in 18.6% of cases. Similarly, lateral femoral cartilage defects were graded as Grade 1 in 34.3%, Grade 2 in 36.3%, and Grade 3 in 15.7%. Patellar and trochlear cartilage defects also showed significant findings, with Grade 4 lesions indicating advanced degeneration. **Hayes et al. (21)** demonstrated correlations between KL grades and MRI findings, noting increased severity of cartilage defects, osteophytes, and meniscal damage with higher KL grades.

Our study compared the diagnostic accuracy of X-ray, US, and MRI in assessing knee OA. Sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy of X-ray with US as a reference were 91.21%, 68.18%, 90.22%, 63.2%, and 83.33%, respectively. In comparison with MRI as the gold standard, X-ray had a sensitivity of 92%, specificity of 84.2%, and accuracy of 92.16%. **Brom et al. (15)** found X-ray sensitivity and specificity at 83% and 93% using US as a reference.

For US versus MRI, sensitivity, specificity, PPV, NPV, and accuracy were 89%, 70%, 97.8%, 56.3%, and 87.25%. **Scheel et al. (22)** noted that US had an overall sensitivity and specificity of 90.5% and 87.5%, respectively, when compared to MRI.

This study confirms that radiography and ultrasonography are valuable tools for knee OA diagnosis. US, with its ability to assess soft tissue, is a useful, non-invasive diagnostic tool, while MRI remains the most accurate but less accessible modality. Further studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to generalize these findings across a broader population.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that osteoarthritis (OA) is more prevalent among females than males in the sample population. Each imaging modality—X-ray, ultrasonography (USG), and MRI—offers unique benefits in assessing OA severity, with X-ray and MRI particularly useful for identifying advanced cases, while USG is more sensitive to detecting early-stage changes. The combination of these imaging techniques enhances diagnostic accuracy, providing a comprehensive view of both bony and soft-tissue changes associated with OA. This approach allows for a more thorough evaluation of OA severity, supporting more effective treatment planning, especially in advanced cases.

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

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Consent: Written consent from participants has been obtained and preserved.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval was obtained and documented as per institutional guidelines.

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